

Information sheet 2.03

Sampling

According to ISPM 31, it is usually not feasible to inspect entire consignments, so phytosanitary inspection is performed mainly on samples obtained from a consignment. It is noted that the sampling concepts presented in this standard may also apply to other phytosanitary procedures, notably selection of units for testing. For inspection, testing and/or surveillance purposes the sample may be taken according to a statistically based or a non-statistical sampling methodology.

This information sheet is a supporting document to Appendix A ('Standardised checklist of risk reduction options') of the Guidance of the EFSA Plant Health Panel on quantitative pest risk assessment.

EFSA PLH Panel (EFSA Panel on Plant Health), Jeger M, Bragard C, Caffier D, Candresse T, Chatzivassiliou E, Dehnen-Schmutz K, Grégoire J-C, Jaques Miret JA, MacLeod A, Navajas Navarro M, Niere B, Parnell S, Potting R, Rafoss T, Rossi V, Urek G, Van Bruggen A, Van der Werf W, West J, Winter S, Hart A, Schans J, Schrader G, Suffert M, Kertész V, Kozelska S, Mannino MR, Mosbach-Schulz O, Pautasso M, Stancanelli G, Tramontini S, Vos S and Gilioli G, 2018. Guidance of the EFSA PLH Panel on quantitative pest risk assessment. *EFSA Journal* 2018;16(7):5350, 94 pp. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2018.5350. Available online at <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2018.5350>

This document is currently still under preparation and will be made available in the near future.